

SEPARATION OF OILS FROM LEATHER WASTE AND DETERMINATION OF THEIR PHYSICOCHEMICAL PROPERTIES

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Abstract. The article presents a comparative analysis of methods for extracting oils from leather waste and the fat-dissolving properties of hexane, gasoline, ethanol and chloroform to select the most suitable solvent for extracting oils.

Keywords: leather waste, oils, solvent, hexane, gasoline, ethanol, chloroform, temperature

Currently, as a result of the increase in the number of manufacturing enterprises and the increase in the volume of production of various products, the emission of various harmful waste from industrial enterprises increases. As a result, they lead to environmental pollution and the emergence of various factors that negatively affect human health.

Therefore, determining the volumes of waste generated at enterprises, creating technologies for their processing and determining the directions for using recycled products are pressing issues.

Leather processing plants also generate large quantities of waste from leather processing (softening or washing, liming, dehairing, tanning and finishing). In most cases, these wastes (unusable hair, subcutaneous fat or skin, as well as leather trimmings separated from finishing) are discharged by the plants into sewers and wastewater, resulting in water pollution.

In terms of the disposal of waste generated as a result of leather processing, it is necessary to substantiate the following scientific decisions: determining the optimal methods for extracting essential oils from leather processing waste, determining the methods for cleaning the obtained essential oils from harmful substances, analysis of the composition of the skin and its waste, as well as essential oils obtained from waste, using various physical and chemical methods, determining the areas of their application have theoretical and practical significance.

For this purpose, samples were taken from leather processing plants, 2 kg of samples were selected, which were carefully cleaned with water from various impurities (small stones, dust, hair). The cleaned sample was dried at a temperature 70°C in a drying cabinet (1, 2, 3 hours), and the yield is calculated using technical scales (table 1)

table 1

Leather waste processing plant

Time required for drying (hours)	Weight sample after drying	Mass obtained after drying	Yield (%)
1	2 kg	1.85 kg	92.5
2	2 kg	1.65 kg	82.5
3	2 kg	1.62 kg	81.0

The table shows that the optimal conditions for drying leather waste are heating at 70°C for 2 hours.

It is known from the literature that the most commonly used solvents for extracting oil are hexane, gasoline, ethanol and chloroform. Considering this, 500 g of cleaned and dried leather waste

was taken and oil extraction was carried out using the above solvents using a Soxhlet extractor to determine the oil extraction yield (Table 2).

table 2

Oil yield from leather processing waste

No	Solvent name	Mass of extracted oil (g)	Yield (%)
1	Chloroform	32.5	6.5%
2	Gasoline	43.5	8.7%
3	Ethanol	62.5	12.5%
4	Heksane	67.5	13.5%

From the table above, it can be seen that the yield of oil from tannery waste was 6.5% in chloroform, 8.7% in gasoline, 12.5% in ethanol and 13.5% in hexane.

The physicochemical parameters of the extracted oil were determined as acid number, iodine number and melting point. To determine the acid number, the number of milligrams of KOH (potassium hydroxide) spent to neutralize 1 g of oil was estimated. For this, 10 g of the sample was taken and dissolved in 50 ml of ethyl alcohol using a water bath.

2-3 drops of phenolphthalein were added to the resulting solution. Solution color. The solution was titrated with 0.1 N alcohol KOH until pink.

Calculation formula:

$$K = \frac{V \times N \times 56.1}{m}$$

Here:

V - the volume of KOH used (ml),

N - the normality of the KOH solution,

m - the mass of fat (g),

56.1 - the equivalent mass of KOH.

Determination of the iodine number The iodine number is determined by the amount of iodine in grams that can bind 100 g of fat. This determines the amount of unsaturated fatty acids.

The experiment is determined by the following steps.

1. 0.5 g of oil is dissolved in chloroform.
2. 25 ml of Hanus solution is added.
3. Keep in the dark for 30 min.
4. 10 ml of 10% potassium iodide solution is added.
5. 100 ml of distilled water is added.
6. The solution is identified with starch and titrated with $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$.

The calculation is carried out according to the following formula.

$$H = \frac{(V_0 - V) \times N \times 12.69}{m}$$

Here:

- V_0 - a blank titration,
 V - a control titration,
 N - the normality of sodium thiosulfate,
 m - the mass of fat (g),

The melting point of fat is the temperature at which the solid state changes to liquid. To do this, a fat sample is placed in a capillary tube, and the tube is placed in a water bath, the temperature is gradually increased ($\sim 1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$). Complete liquefaction of the fat is heated - this temperature is taken as the melting point. The results obtained from the above experiments are summarized in Table 3.

table 3

Physicochemical parameters of oil

Name of parametr	Quantity
Acid number, mg KOH/g,	0,77
Iodine number, g $\text{J}_2/100$ g, no more than	34,18
Melting point, $^\circ\text{C}$	46,5

From the above, it can be concluded that hexane is the most suitable solvent for extracting oil from leather waste. Because hexane has a lower boiling point than other solvents and has the best fat-dissolving properties. It was also determined that the acid value was 0.77, the iodine value was 34.18, and the melting point was 46.5. The experimental results obtained provide scientific guidance for determining the application areas of oils obtained from leather waste.

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